

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Use of Potato and Curry Leaves for Anti-Ageing Cream

Aayushi Yelgurwar*, Chhavi Rahangdale, Divyani Dahake, Harshada Borekar,
Mitali Bodhankar

Gurunanak College of Pharmacy, Kashi Nagar, Bank Colony, Nagpur, Maharashtra 440026

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27 May 2024

Accepted: 31 May 2024

Published: 12 June 2024

Keywords:

Ageing, Anti-ageing,
Antioxidants, Solanum
tuberosum, Murraya koenigii,
Cosmetological,
 β -caryophyllene,
Rutaceae, Ageing, premature.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11609456

ABSTRACT

Creams are considered an important part of cosmetic product as topical preparations from time immemorial due to their ease of application to the skin and also their removal. From cosmetic purposes, Pharmaceutical creams have a variety of applications such as cleansing, beautifying, altering appearance, moisturizing etc. to skin protection against bacterial, fungal infections as well as healing cuts, burns, wounds on the skin. Skin aging is a complex biological process influenced by a combination of endogenous or intrinsic and exogenous or extrinsic factors. Because of the fact that skin health and beauty is considered one of the principal factors representing overall “well-being” and the perception of “health” in humans, several anti-aging strategies have been developed during the last years. It is the intention of this article to review the most important anti-aging strategies that dermatologists have nowadays in hand, including preventive measurements, cosmetological strategies, topical and systemic therapeutic agents and invasive procedures. Potato contains zinc, sulphur and copper, these are effective as controlling acne, and eliminating toxins from the skin. Potatoes are effective at diminishing premature signs of ageing and lightening of skin because they contains antioxidants and glow inducing vitamin A, B and C. Curry leaves are an important part of spicing up dishes, thus used for garnishing as well as a taste enhancer. Apart from its culinary uses, it has a vast number of therapeutic applications in medicinal as well as cosmetic uses. Curry leaves, biologically named as *Murraya koenigii* which belongs to family Rutaceae. It has a characteristic aroma. It is an important herb mainly of Asian origin. The present review elaborates the description of curry leaves, its chemical composition and about the bioactive compound β -caryophyllene present in it. β -caryophyllene is a sesquiterpene, it has properties such as inhibition of melanogenesis and can reduce melanin synthesis. Curry leaves cream is formulated for the purpose of reduction of dark spots due to presence of β -caryophyllene present in curry leaves.

***Corresponding Author:** Aayushi Yelgurwar

Address: Gurunanak College of Pharmacy, Kashi Nagar, Bank Colony, Nagpur, Maharashtra 440026

Email ✉: aayushiyelgurwar09@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are pharmaceutical products that are used for improving skin appearance and body odour. These products are available in various forms, ranging from lotions, creams, powders, gel, shampoo, hair mask, face mask, lipstick, and so forth. Cosmetics are used for cleansing, protecting, and moisturizing the skin. Generally, consumers prefer to choose cosmetics that have less harmful effects on their skin. "Cosmeceutical" products have now been developed by many pharmaceutical industries. A cosmeceutical is the combination of a topical cosmetic and a pharmaceutical that is used for enhancing beauty through ingredients that have biological functions related to the skin. Ageing is a natural process in human life. Along with increasing age, all aspects of our body show the effects of ageing. These changes occur naturally. Exposure to UV light results in the formation of free radicals from ROS (Radical Oxygen Species) which trigger chain reactions, resulting in damage to cell components such as fats, proteins and nucleic acids. Ageing could be seen from seven main signs such as fine lines and wrinkles, changes in skin colour and texture, dull skin surface, visible pores, blotches, age spots and dryness. Among all these signs, the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles on the skin is the most common sign of aging. The periorbital area is often one of the first areas to show signs of aging. Although this condition is not physically harmful, it has various psychosocial and functional effects. Common impressions related to periorbital ageing are looking tired, sad, or angry. One of the natural ingredients that is empirically used by the public as eye compresses is yellow potatoes. Vitamin C and flavonoids are chemical compounds present in potatoes that have antioxidant activity. Vitamin C can function as an oxygen scavenger by transferring hydrogen atoms to oxygen so that oxygen is not available for subsequent reactions.

Here we have made a vanishing cream out of POTATO and CURRY LEAVES.

POTATO:

The ritual of using potatoes for skincare dates back 5000 years ago. According to archaeological archives, potato slices were used by medicine men in Peru as a soothing remedy for skin burn. In some countries, it was also used as soap. Potato fights visible signs of ageing. Potatoes contain vitamin C which is an essential nutrient for collagen building. It strengthens your skin and fights visible signs of ageing like fine lines and wrinkles.

Botanical Classification:

Kingdom: Plantae

Subkingdom: Viridiaeplantae

Division: tracheophyte

Subdivision: Spermatophytina

Class: Mangoliopsida

Order: Solanales

Family: Solanaceae

Genus: Solanum

Species: Solanum tuberosum Linn.–

Chemical constituents:

it contains phenolics, flavonoids, kukoamines, anthocyanins, carotenoids, alkaloids, carbohydrates, starch, Phytochemistry : A new tuber-inducing stimulus isolated from leaves and characterised as 3-oxo-2(5'- B-D-glucopyranosyloxy-2'(Z)-pentenyl)cyclopentane-1-acetic acid, scopolin an anthocyanin petanin isolated from acidified methanolic extract of blue tubers and characterised as petunidin-3-O-[6-O-(4-O-(E)-p-coumaroyl-a-L-rhamnopyranosyl)- B-D-glucopyranosido]-5-O-B-D-glucopyranoside seeds afforded two steroid glycosides tuberosides C and D - whose structures determined , another glycoside - tuberoside F- from seeds and its absolute configuration. A Russet potato, one of the favourite varieties in North America, contains the second highest antioxidants. Apart from starch, crude fiber, vitamins, amino acids, and minerals, the tubers incorporate various phenolic

compounds which constitute the bulk of natural antioxidants.

Nutritional value:

Potatoes have been found to be a particularly nutritious vegetable. Starch is the predominant aspect of potatoes, but they also contain small amounts of protein and alkaline salts. They are complex carbohydrate in the form of sugars, practically free of fats and cholesterol. Large amount of vitamins present in potato are beta-carotene, vitamin C, A, B1, B2, B6, and Folic acid. Many of the Nutrients in potatoes are found in their skin.

Uses:

- Potatoes show strong antioxidant capacity among most frequently consumed vegetables. Solanum changes skin condition better with an increase in water content (45.2%), smaller pores (8%), an increase in smoothness (31.9%), reduction of blemishes (57.37 %) and wrinkles (41.8%).
- Some glossary declared a component named Azelaic Acid from Potato do inhibits tyrosinase activity to reduce pigmentation spotting related to breakouts, treats mild to moderate acne (both inflammatory and comedonal), reduces bacteria growth in the follicles, scavenges free radicals. extracts potato starch. Used as a thickening agent in cosmetics.
- Phenolics and amino acids present with antioxidant protection towards tissue damage, reactive oxygen species and diseases like atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, renal failure, and cancer.
- Potatoes are a good source of vitamin C, which is an antioxidant that helps protect cells from damage, supports the immune system, and helps with collagen synthesis, which is important for healthy skin.

Other uses:

- **Potato Juice Heals Sun-Damaged Skin:** Potatoes contain polyphenols that protect your skin against sun damage and ensure even skin tone. Potato is rich in zinc which heals your skin and soothes inflammation.
- **Potato Juice On Face Helps For Brightening Complexion:** Potatoes are enriched with the goodness of iron which brightens your skin tone, leaving it healthy and radiant.
- **Applying Potato Juice On Face Helps To Fight Acne:** Azelaic acid found in potatoes fights pimples and redness, leaving your skin healthy and clear. It can unclog your pores and help you get rid of dead skin cells.
- **Fights Visible Signs Of Ageing:** Potatoes contain vitamin C which is an essential nutrient for collagen building. It strengthens your skin and fights visible signs of ageing like fine lines and wrinkles.
- **Potato Juice Moisturises Skin:** Potato is an excellent ingredient to moisturise and hydrate your skin from within. It improves skin health and leaves your skin glowing.

CURRY LEAVES:

Apart from its culinary uses, it has a vast number of therapeutic applications in medicinal as well as cosmetic uses. It has a characteristic aroma. It is an important herb mainly of Asian origin. Curry leaves are rich in nutrients like vitamin E, which can help nourish the skin, improve its texture, and provide protection against skin-related issues.

Biological classification:

Kingdom-Plantae

Subkingdom- Tracheobionta

Superdivision- Spermatophyta

Division- Magnoliophyta
Class- Magnoliopsida
Subclass - Rosidae
Family- Rutaceae
Genus- *Murraya J. Koenig ex L.*
Species- *Murraya koenigii (L.) Spreng*

Chemical constituents:

the leaves of *Murraya koenigii* contain koenimbine, O-methyl murrayamine, O-methyl mahanine, isomahanine, bismahanine, and bispyrayafoline, as well as koenigine, koenine, koenidine, mahanimbine, isomahanimbine, koenimbidine and murrayacine, isomahanimbicine, Euchrest The glycozoline, 1-formyl-3-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole, and 6, 7-dimethoxy-1-hydroxy-3-methyl carbazole are the main components of dried leaves. Additionally, *Murraya koenigii*'s leaves contain nicotinic acid, protein, carbs, fibre, minerals, and carotene.

Nutritional value:

The plant leaves contain a substantial amount of proximate composition; the moisture is 63.2%, protein is 8.8%, carbohydrate is 39.4%, total nitrogen is 1.15%, fat is 6.15%, total sugars are 18.92%, starch is 14.6%, and crude fiber is 6.8%. The leaves have been reported as a significant source of several vitamins, such as vitamin A (B-carotene), with a level of 6.04 ± 0.02 mg/100g; vitamin B3, (niacin), with a level of 2.73 ± 0.02 mg/100 g; vitamin B1 (thiamin), with a level of 0.89 ± 0.01 mg/100 g; calcium, with a level of 19.73 ± 0.02 mg/100 g; magnesium, with a level of 49.06 ± 0.02 mg/100 g; and sodium, with a level of 16.50 ± 0.21 mg/100 g. The alcohol-soluble extract has a value of 1.82%, ash has a value of 13.06%, acid-insoluble ash has a value of 1.35%, cold water (20 °C) extractive has a value of 27.33%, and maximum of hot-water-soluble extractive has a value of 33.45% [15,45]. Wide ranges of carbazole alkaloids, essential oils, terpenoids, and flavonoids have numerous beneficial roles.

Uses:

Reduces Wrinkles:

The curry leaf powder's antioxidant capabilities help prevent premature aging of the skin by reducing fine lines and wrinkles. Environmental exposure, particularly exposure to the sun, is the main cause of premature aging. As previously noted, curry leaf powder is high in antioxidants, which help to promote new cell growth while also reducing the effects of premature aging.

Flawless Skin:

Curry leaf powder has wonderful qualities that make your face glow and shine and is fantastic for treating acne. Curry leaf powder is rich in antioxidants, has anti-microbial qualities, and certain important vitamins for the skin, like vitamins A and C, which are highly beneficial for maintaining healthy skin.

Treatment Acne Scars:

Curry leaf powder is a powerful anti-bacterial that eliminates a wide variety of bacteria that can result in fungus infections and acne outbreaks. And because of its antioxidant-rich formula, which also balances excess skin oil, reduces pore size, neutralizes free radical damage, and treats acne scars and markings, your skin will stay healthy.

Anti-Inflammatory Properties:

Numerous anti-inflammatory substances can be found in curry leaf powder. These anti-inflammatory qualities lessen the signs and discomfort brought on by fungal and acne infections. The anti-microbial qualities of curry leaf powder also guarantee that it will provide defense against free radicals, fungi, bug bites, and acne.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

FORMULATION:

Vanishing Cream : It is an oil in water type of emulsion. It is a cosmetic cream that is colourless once applied, used as a foundation for powder or as a cleansing or moisturizer cream. The powder sticks to the cream perfectly and left a dry, non-oily finish. It is a light weight, oil free cream that is ideal for oily or combination skin types and provides a smooth, matte finish. It protects against chapping in cold weather and wind and keep skin looking younger longer. The potato and curry leaves cream was formulated by the ingredients given below. The cream was prepared by fusion method considering the nutritional values of *Solanum tuberosum* and *Murraya koenigii*. Oil in water cream was formulated. Both the drugs chosen consists of many antioxidants which gives free radical scavenging activity resulting in anti-ageing. The formulated cream possesses ANTI-AGEING activity.

FORMULA

Sr.no.	Ingredients	Quantity
01	Stearic acid	20g
02	Triethanolamine	2g
03	Glycerine	14g
04	Potassiumhydroxide	1g
05	Sodium lauryl sulphate(SLS)	0.5g
06	Methyl paraben	0.5g
07	Propyl paraben	0.5g
08	Distilled Water	65g
09	Perfume (rose water)	q.s

Materials:

1. Stearic acid :

It governs the consistency of the cream and imparts pearlescent property to the cream by forming crystals. It is ideal as an emulsifying agent and great for skin products.

2. Triethanolamine :

These provide cream with less lustre. It helps stabilize consistency improve texture, and facilitate easy spreadability of the products. TEA also acts as a buffering agent, ensuring the desired PH level of the cosmetics formulation.

3. Glycerine:

It provides excessive drying of the cream. It helped to soften and protect the skin and prevent chaps. Glycerine also acted as a humectant which helped prevent the vanishing cream from drying out while it sat on the shelf.

4. Potassium hydroxide :

It imparts fine texture and consistency without providing harshness. KOH is used to sink the CO₂ bubbles rose at the top of the cream mixture.

5. Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS):

It is most often used as an emulsifier or surfactant. As an emulsifier, SLS helps to stabilize and thicken solution with ingredients of differing

solution. This allows products to achieve a more uniform texture for easier, and smoother application.

6. Methyl paraben:

Methyl paraben is a preservative. It is used to prevent the growth of pathogens and stop undesirable chemical changes from occurring. Thus, these chemicals can protect both the products and the consumer.

7. Propyl paraben:

Propyl paraben is a stable, non-volatile compounds used as an antimicrobial preservative in foods, drugs and cosmetics for over 50 years. Propyl paraben is readily absorbed via the gastrointestinal tract and dermis.

8. Distilled water:

provides stability to the cream because hard water leads to the formation of the magnesium causing inversion of emulsion. It reduces loss of moisture from dry skin.

9. Perfume:

Imparts odour to the preparation. (Examples: sandal wood, lavender oil, rose water) Here we have added rose water.

APPARATUS :

Water bath, Weighing Balance, Beaker, Glass rod, Measuring cylinder, Thermometer, Butter paper, Whatmann filter paper, Spatula, Funnel, Tripod stand, Glass stirrer, Mortar Pestle, Petri plates, Tongs.

EXTRACTION METHOD :

POTATO

1. 350 g of potato were taken and wash the potatoes with clean water and then peel off them.
2. Slice the potatoes into small pieces and then shade dry it on a clean cotton cloth till the moisture content remain to be minimum into it .
3. The crude powder of potato was made using mixer grinder.

CURRY LEAVES

1. 350 of curry leaves were taken and wash the curry leaves with clean water.
2. Sorting out the curry leaves and shade dry it on a clean cotton cloth till it completely dry
3. The crude powder of dried curry leaves was made using mixer grinder

MACERATION:

1. Both the crude powders were weighed separately on the weighing balance.
2. For extraction of active components maceration method was performed. Powdered plant materials were soaked in 80 : 20 i.e., ethanol : water solvents respectively.
3. The material was kept aside for 2 days with occasional stirring and allowed to macerate accordingly.
4. The macerate was filtered with whatmann filter paper and the filtrate and residue was separated.
5. Extracts were collected and poured in petri plated and allowed to vaporise the solvent i.e., ethanol completely so that no traceable amount of ethanol remain into the extract.
6. After evaporation process extract was scraped out with the help of spatula and then used for formulation of anti-ageing vanishing cream.

FORMULATION PROCEDURE:

Aqueous phase:

triethanolamine, glycerine, potassium hydroxide, SLS, water, curry leaves and potato extract.

Oil phase: stearic acid, curry leaves extract.

1. Stearic acid melted in a container by using a water bath.
2. (beaker 1.... Oil phase) Potassium hydroxide and triethanolamine were dissolved in water and glycerine is added and heated to the temperature of 75°C. (beaker 2.....aqueous phase).
3. Slowly aqueous phase i.e., beaker 2 solution is added to the melted stearic acid i.e., beaker 2
4. Perfume(rose water) is added to the preparation when it attains 40°C.

EVALUATION TESTS :

1. Determination of pH :

The pH of the cream can be measured on a standard digital pH meter at room temperature by taking adequate amount of the formulation diluted with a suitable solvent in a suitable beaker.

2. Physical appearance :

The physical appearance of the cream can be observed by its colour, roughness and graded.

3. Spreadability :

Adequate amount of sample is taken between two glass slides and a weight of 100gm is applied on the slides for 5 minutes. Spreadability can be expressed as,

$$S = m \cdot l / t$$

Where, m = weight applied to upper slide.

l = length moved on the glass slide.

t = time taken.

4. Acid value :

10gm of substance is dissolved in accurately weighed 50ml mixture of equal volume of alcohol and solvent ether, the flask was connected to reflux condenser and slowly heated, until sample was dissolved completely, to this 1ml of phenolphthalein added and titrated with 0.1N NaOH, until faintly pink colour appears after shaking for 30 seconds.

$$\text{Acid value} = n \cdot 5.61 / w$$

Where,

n = the no. of ml of 0.1 N KOH solution.

w = the weight of substance in gram

5. Viscosity :

Viscosity of formulated creams can be determined by using Brookfield Viscometer

6. Homogeneity :

The formulation was tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

7. Removal :

The ease of removal of the creams applied was examined by washing the applied part with tap water.

8. Dye test :

The scarlet dye is mixed with the cream. Place a drop of cream in a slide and cover with a cover slip and examine it under a microscope. If the disperse globule

9. appears red and the ground colourless then it is o/w type and the reverse condition appears in w/o type of creams.

10. After feel :

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of fixed amount of cream was checked.

11. Type of smear :

After application of cream, the type of film or smear formed on the skin were checked.

12. Irritancy study:

Mark an area of 1sq.cm on the left hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema was checked, if any, for regular intervals upto 24 hours and reported

13. Accelerated Stability Study :

Accelerated stability study is conducted for formulation according to ICH guidelines.

RESULTS OF EVALUATION :

Sr.no.	parameters	Observation
1	Appearance	Yellowish-white
2	Odour	Slightly aromatic
3	Ph	6.5
4	Dye test	o/w type
5	Patch test	No hypersensitiveness
6	Type of smear	Non-greasy
7	Emolliency	No residue left
8	Viscosity	-
9	Consistency	Good
10	Washability	washable

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The project was planned for the effective anti-ageing cream for dark circles and wrinkles considering the active constituents and the traditional use. The extraction of active constituents was done, and it was incorporated in the vanishing cream formulation. Because of its known anti-ageing properties the formula can be very well used for antiaging as well as antiwrinkle properties. The project formulation has potential for commercialization.

CONCLUSION:

In ancient system of medicine or in Ayurvedic formulation initially the household practices were used for beautifying purposes and (reference) and to find the purpose we have formulated a cream for anti-ageing. We have got the references from various journals and the literatures (compendium glossary etc). the cream prepared has effective properties. Based on analysis we have concluded that the extracts have its use in anti-ageing properties. It can be useful in future ways.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

It would not have been possible to write this project without the help and support of the kind people around me. It is possible to give particular mention here. I would like to express my sincere

appreciation and heartfelt thanks to my kind supervisor Dr. MITALI BODHANKAR, Associate Professor Gurunanak College of Pharmacy, Nagpur, for his creative guidance, intellectual support, stimulating discussions, inspiring words and valuable advice.

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HOW TO CITE: Aayushi Yelgurwar, Chhavi Rahangdale, Divyani Dahake, Harshada Borekar, Mitali Bodhankar, Use Of Potato And Curry Leaves For Anti-Ageing Cream, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 6, 623-633. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11609456>

